

MARKETING ANALYSIS OF DRUGS USED IN OBSTETRICS AND GYNECOLOGY

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Relevance: at present, the prevalence of obstetric and gynecological diseases is increasing worldwide, which makes this issue one of the most urgent problems in the global healthcare system. According to the World Health Organization, diseases affecting women's reproductive health have not only medical but also socio-economic consequences. The rise in these conditions is associated with several factors, including ecological, socio-economic, nutritional and lifestyle-related, infectious, demographic, as well as genetic and endocrine factors. Statistical data indicate that polycystic ovary syndrome, endometriosis, uterine fibroids, cervical cancer, and vaginitis are among the most common disorders globally. In obstetric and gynecological practice, medicinal products are primarily used to facilitate labor, ensure contraception, preserve or terminate pregnancy, treat hormonal imbalances, and prevent or manage infections. Based on these aspects, conducting a marketing analysis of drugs used in this field within the local pharmaceutical market is highly relevant.

Purpose of the study: to conduct a marketing analysis of the pharmaceutical market of the Republic of Uzbekistan regarding medicinal products used in obstetric and gynecological practice.

Materials and methods: the study was carried out using data from the State Register of Medicinal Products, Medical Devices, and Medical Equipment permitted for use in medical practice in the Republic of Uzbekistan for the years 2020–2024. The drug assortment was analyzed employing content analysis as well as assortment breadth, completeness, depth, and renewal index as methodological approaches.

Results: the analysis of drugs used in obstetrics and gynecology by pharmacotherapeutic groups revealed the following: in 2020, a total of 55 drugs were registered (foreign – 48, CIS – 5, local – 2), whereas in 2021 the figure increased to 77 (foreign – 62, CIS – 4, local – 11). In 2022, 83 drugs were recorded (foreign – 65, CIS – 4, local – 14), in 2023 – 78 (foreign – 62, CIS – 2, local – 14), and in 2024 – 69 (foreign – 53, CIS – 2, local – 14). Thus, the drug assortment expanded in 2021–2022, but a gradual decline was observed in 2023–2024. Foreign drugs accounted for the majority each year (87% in 2020 and 77% in 2024). Nevertheless, the share of locally produced drugs increased steadily: from 3.6% in 2020 to 20.3% in 2024. Among the pharmacotherapeutic groups, G01A (antimicrobial agents and antiseptics) represented the largest segment. The number of foreign products in this group rose from 22 in 2020 to 43 in 2022 and remained stable thereafter, while local production appeared in 2022 (10–12 items). G02 (other gynecological preparations) demonstrated a gradual decrease (15 in 2020 vs. 4 in 2024). G02A (uterotonic drugs), represented by one item in 2020, expanded with the introduction of local alternatives in 2022–2024, indicating the development of domestic production. G03X (sex hormones and modulators of the genital system) remained stable with 1–2 foreign drugs annually. L02A (hormone antagonists and related agents) and H01B (pituitary posterior lobe hormones) did not change, consistently showing 1–2 foreign drugs per year. J01X and J02A (systemic antibacterials and antifungals) were rarely used, appearing only in certain years. Furthermore, non-classified drugs were identified: 3 in 2020, 6 in 2022, and 4 in 2024, reflecting existing challenges in classification and standardization.

Conclusions: the increase in obstetric and gynecological diseases is associated with complex factors and requires comprehensive research, early diagnosis, and the development of effective treatment approaches. During 2020–2024, the market of drugs used in obstetrics and gynecology was dominated by foreign products, although local production has been gradually strengthening. The most significant progress has been observed in the production of antimicrobial and uterotonic drugs. At the same time, reducing the number of non-classified drugs and aligning them with the ATC system remains an important scientific and practical task for the future.